

Research Question	Category	Code	Definition	Number of Participants	Example Quotes	Participants falling in this code
RQ1	Verification Source	Independent_SMS_Verification	Merchants relying on receiving an independent SMS notification on their own device to confirm that a payment has been successfully received.	24	"Checking on my phone is the most reliable way for me because when the money comes in, you receive a message and immediately see that the balance has increased. Honestly, this is the only method I trust." (P-11)	P-2, P-3, P-4, P-5, P-6, P-7, P-8, P-9, P-10, P-11, P-12, P-13, P-14, P-15, P-16, P-19, P-20, P-22, P-23, P-24, P-25, P-26, P-27, P-28
RQ1	Verification Source	Visual_Inspection_of_Customer_Screen	Merchants inspecting the customer's phone screen (SMS or USSD pop-up) to verify payment, often used as a secondary method when the merchant's phone is unavailable or network is slow.	13	"Most look at messages on the customer's phone. Often in that work, if they're controlling, they're far away, requiring you to confirm you've paid to a waiter, requiring you to show them on your phone." (P-22)	P-2, P-4, P-6, P-9, P-11, P-13, P-14, P-16, P-20, P-22, P-24, P-25, P-28
RQ1	Verification Source	Social_Trust_Verification	Merchants accepting a verbal claim of payment or a quick glance without rigorous verification, often based on interpersonal relationships, familiarity, or social pressure.	12	"It happens a lot. Especially when there are people we know each other well enough to trust each other." (P-16)	P-3, P-6, P-7, P-11, P-13, P-16, P-19, P-20, P-21, P-23, P-25, P-29
RQ1	Verification Source	Manual_Balance_Check	Merchants actively inquiring about their balance or checking transaction history logs when SMS notifications fail to arrive.	6	"MTN messages often delay, so I check my balance to confirm. If I had 1000 before and now it's 2000, I know I was paid—even if the message came late." (P-15)	P-2, P-8, P-12, P-15, P-23, P-26
RQ1	Operational Drivers	Network_Latency_Workaround	Delays in SMS delivery or network failures forcing merchants to abandon standard verification and rely on alternative, less secure methods (like looking at customer screens).	9	"Actually sometimes we do worry when sending or paying, because sometimes the message delays. When it finally arrives it's because of MTN network delays—that's the problem we get." (P-4)	P-4, P-6, P-7, P-9, P-10, P-13, P-14, P-22, P-24
RQ1	Operational Drivers	High_Volume_Pressure	High customer traffic or rush hours compelling merchants to skip rigorous checks to maintain service speed.	6	"Sometimes, a lot of them come and show me their payment confirmation screens telling me they've paid, but can't confirm because I have many customers at that particular time." (P-13)	P-7, P-11, P-13, P-19, P-22, P-27
RQ1	Operational Drivers	Device_Unavailability	Situations where the merchant's verification device is dead, charging, or physically absent, leading to reliance on the customer's proof.	4	"I ask them when I don't have the phone near me, it died for example or the battery is dead or something that requires going to charge. I tell them show me your SMS you sent let me see." (P-28)	P-6, P-14, P-15, P-28
RQ1	Verification Heuristic	Sender_ID_Validation	Actively checking that the SMS sender is "MobileMoney" or a specific service code, rather than a personal phone number, to detect spoofing.	8	"I check the message. First, it must be clear that it was sent by MoMo to my phone. I check that it is 'M-Money...'" (P-19)	P-2, P-3, P-9, P-10, P-11, P-15, P-19, P-24
RQ1	Verification Heuristic	Timestamp_Scrutiny	Rigorously checking the date and time within the SMS to ensure the proof is not a recycled screenshot or old message.	7	"I go into my messages and check if the message is from the correct date and time, because someone may show you a fake or old message." (P-24)	P-3, P-7, P-11, P-14, P-22, P-24, P-28
RQ1	Verification Heuristic	Name_Matching_Check	Verifying that the recipient name displayed on the customer's confirmation screen matches the merchant's specific registered name.	9	"The key parts in mobile money are, first, the names—I check if the names are mine." (P-3)	P-3, P-5, P-8, P-11, P-13, P-14, P-15, P-16, P-23
RQ1	Verification Heuristic	Exact_Amount_Confirmation	Focusing primarily or exclusively on the numerical amount in the message to ensure it matches the agreed price.	10	"But the most important thing I check here is the amount. Because the phone number has many digits... so I just focus on the amount." (P-7)	P-7, P-8, P-11, P-14, P-16, P-19, P-20, P-23, P-24, P-27
RQ1	Verification Heuristic	USSD_Popup_Reliance	Relying on the temporary flash message (USSD response) that appears immediately after dialing, rather than the final SMS.	4	"It's the one you see after the star code." (P-16)	P-3, P-16, P-17, P-20
RQ1	Verification Heuristic	Screenshot_Forensics	Merchants actively looking for visual signs of image editing or messy formatting to identify fake screenshots.	3	"I realized it because the screenshot looked messy or disorganized." (P-11)	P-11, P-20, P-24
RQ1	Verification Heuristic	Audio_Notification_Cue	Relying on the sound of the phone notification as a proxy for verification without unlocking the device to read the text.	4	"Sometimes I wait for the notification sound to confirm the payment because I don't have someone who can check the message." (P-13)	P-7, P-11, P-13, P-27
RQ1	Verification Source	Transaction_History_Audit	Navigating into the MoMo menu or requesting a mini-statement to verify recent transactions when SMS is missing.	5	"I look at the transaction history and check the balance. I don't rely solely on the phone's vibration." (P-10)	P-10, P-12, P-14, P-21, P-28
RQ1	Verification Source	Inter-Spousal_Verification	Merchants calling or checking with a spouse/partner who holds the registered SIM to confirm receipt of funds.	3	"I call my child and tell them someone paid me. But if we both got the messages at the same time, it would be good." (P-24)	P-24, P-27, P-28
RQ1	Verification Source	Staff_Delegation_Check	Relying on an employee or attendant to verify the payment on a shared work device.	4	"That happens quite often because when we're working, one person is usually giving out the goods. So that person might tell you, 'Check if this amount has come in.'" (P-11)	P-4, P-11, P-19, P-22
RQ1	Verification Source	Paper_Ledger_Reconciliation	Using a physical notebook to record sales and cross-referencing it with digital balance/messages later.	2	"You calculate by checking what is written in the notebook and matching it with the amount of money they give you." (P-19)	P-19, P-27
RQ1	Operational Drivers	Battery_Conservation_Strategy	Forcing reliance on the customer's screen because the merchant's phone battery is low or dead.	3	"Sometimes I tell them my phone is out of battery... In that case, the only way to be sure the money has arrived is by checking the balance." (P-15)	P-15, P-28, P-6
RQ1	Operational Drivers	Transaction_Value_Threshold	Applying stricter verification for large amounts while relaxing checks for small amounts.	3	"I pay more attention when the amount is large, but for small amounts like 500, I don't spend much time on it." (P-19)	P-11, P-19, P-23
RQ1	Operational Drivers	Social_Etiquette_Constraint	Choosing not to inspect the customer's phone or demand proof to avoid offending the customer or implying distrust.	2	"It reduces the customer feeling offended because when you ask the customer to show you, they feel like it's our culture that you don't believe them." (P-22)	P-11, P-22
RQ1	Operational Drivers	Language_Barrier_Friction	Difficulty in verifying confirmation messages because they are displayed in English rather than Kinyarwanda.	2	"Another thing is that on MoMo, messages sometimes come in English, which makes it difficult for us to know when it went through." (P-11)	P-2, P-11
RQ1	Operational Drivers	Physical_Separation_Constraint	Challenges in verifying payments when the payer is not physically present (e.g., sent by a relative or remote buyer).	4	"The only challenge is when you're not physically together, since it requires them to enter the code." (P-7)	P-7, P-21, P-22, P-27
RQ1	Verification Workflow	Goods_Retention_Policy	Physically withholding goods or preventing the customer from leaving until the SMS arrives.	3	"If I haven't yet received the payment message, I can't let the customer go." (P-11)	P-11, P-19, P-27
RQ1	Verification Workflow	Double_Confirmation_Protocol	Treating digital verification with the same immediate scrutiny as counting physical cash.	2	"It's like when a customer gives you cash, you count it. When they pay by phone, you must see the money arrived." (P-24)	P-12, P-24
RQ1	Verification Workflow	Delayed_Batch_Verification	Checking payments in a batch at the end of a shift or day rather than per transaction.	2	"I usually find out when calculating at the end of the sales." (P-13)	P-13, P-27
RQ1	Verification Workflow	Call_Center_Escalation	Calling the telecom provider (MTN) immediately to trace a transaction when verification fails in the moment.	4	"If it doesn't come, we contact MTN to trace the transaction." (P-11)	P-4, P-7, P-11, P-16
RQ1	Trust Dynamic	Familiarity_Relaxation	Reducing verification steps (skipping checks) for known neighbors or repeat customers.	7	"A regular customer might say, 'Give me this item...' The way I verify their payment is not the same as with a new customer." (P-11)	P-11, P-12, P-13, P-14, P-16, P-23, P-25
RQ1	Trust Dynamic	Zero_Trust_Default	Adopting a policy of never trusting a customer's word or screen, regardless of appearance.	6	"I don't trust—I check. Anyone, even a neighbor, I check." (P-24)	P-5, P-9, P-10, P-17, P-23, P-24
RQ1	Trust Dynamic	Appearance_Bias	Being more likely to trust (or be scammed by) customers who are well-dressed or appear respectable.	2	"Sometimes you meet a well-dressed person... later, when I checked, she hadn't paid." (P-15)	P-10, P-15
RQ1	Verification Source	Multi-SIM_Check	Checking multiple phones or SIM cards because the merchant manages multiple accounts.	2	"There's another one that stays at work that we use very rarely... so they can check and verify." (P-6)	P-6, P-15
RQ1	Verification Workflow	Inbox_Hygiene_Strategy	Deliberately deleting old messages or organizing the inbox to prevent confusion between new and old payments during verification.	2	"But when messages become many, it can be confusing to identify who paid you. So it is better to reduce or delete them to clearly know who paid you at a given time." (P-25)	P-25, P-28
RQ1	Verification Workflow	Pre-Payment_Mandate	A strict policy of requiring successful verification before providing the service or handing over goods to mitigate risk.	4	"I make sure they pay before I serve them." (P-8)	P-8, P-9, P-11, P-12
RQ1	Verification Heuristic	PIN_Entry_Observation	Merchants watching the customer physically type their PIN as a validation step, knowing that fake apps or screenshots don't require PIN entry.	3	"If they just tell me without entering the Momo PIN and cancel the transaction, how would I know it's real?" (P-14)	P-14, P-15, P-22
RQ1	Verification Heuristic	Sequential_Balance_Tracking	Mentally or physically calculating the expected new balance (Previous Balance + Transaction Amount) to verify the incoming fund.	2	"If I had 20,000 RWF before and they pay me 100,000 RWF, I check to see if my balance has increased to 120,000 RWF." (P-23)	P-23, P-28
RQ1	Verification Heuristic	Top-Line_Scanning	Rapidly reading only the first line of the SMS (Sender/Amount) and ignoring the rest to save time during rush hours.	2	"The top line usually says you have received money. The rest is further below, but you first look at the amount received." (P-24)	P-24, P-27
RQ1	Verification Source	Remote_Payer_Validation	Verifying payments made by a third party (not the person present), often requiring a phone call to the remote sender.	3	"The merchant told me he had not received the money, yet when I called my wife, she told me she had already sent it." (P-21)	P-21, P-22, P-28

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RQ1	Trust Dynamic	Deferred_Verification	Allowing a trusted customer to leave immediately, with the merchant performing the verification asynchronously later.	3	"Some leave. I check later and trust that they have paid. Later I check and find that they paid." (P-25)	P-16, P-25, P-6
RQ1	Operational Drivers	Cross-Network_Confusion	Verification difficulties arising when users send money between different networks (MTN vs Airtel) or receive scam messages from competing networks.	3	"The message was actually a MoMo message sent from an Airtel number. If you don't check carefully, you could lose money this way." (P-10)	P-10, P-16, P-19
RQ1	Verification Workflow	Screenshot_Rejection	An explicit policy of refusing to accept screenshots as valid proof due to the high prevalence of editing fraud.	3	"I check on mine too. Otherwise you might be fooled by someone sending a fake screenshot." (P-24)	P-11, P-22, P-24
RQ1	Operational Drivers	Customer_Resistance	Customers actively refusing to show their screens or hand over phones for verification due to privacy or hurry, forcing the merchant to find other ways.	3	"Some even refuse to show it and tell you to check your own phone instead." (P-11)	P-11, P-21, P-25
RQ1	Trust Dynamic	Reciprocal_Trust	Merchants trusting customers because they believe the customer trusts them (social contract).	1	"I trust them... Because if you don't trust, that way there's nothing you'd achieve." (P-29)	P-29
RQ2	Digital Forgery	Static_Screenshot_Reuse	Fraudsters presenting a screenshot of a legitimate past transaction (with modified or ignored date/time) to simulate a new payment.	8	"He had 'paid' — when I checked the balance it was gone... discovered he had a way of editing one message and sending it... the message someone sends to show they've paid can be edited." (P-11)	P-7, P-11, P-12, P-13, P-20, P-22, P-24, P-28
RQ2	Digital Forgery	SMS_Content_Spoofing	The creation of fake SMS notifications that mimic the format and sender ID of official Mobile Money receipts to deceive merchants.	7	"Someone sent me a fake message that looked exactly like the real one... The message even had my name, but the balance shown didn't match mine." (P-15)	P-4, P-11, P-15, P-19, P-20, P-22, P-25
RQ2	Digital Forgery	Simulated_Transaction_Flow	Fraudsters initiating a payment to generate the "Confirm Name" USSD pop-up, showing this to the merchant as proof, but never entering the PIN to complete the transfer.	6	"They show the first message before they put the pin and then the owner of the bar later discovered after a few days that they didn't pay." (P-13)	P-3, P-12, P-13, P-15, P-22, P-25
RQ2	Digital Forgery	Airtime_Masquerade	Sending an Airtime transfer (or showing an Airtime SMS) which looks similar to a cash transfer SMS, tricking merchants into releasing goods for "air" instead of money.	3	"I asked that agent, they told me 'this is air they sent, this message of money is air,' I didn't know there were air messages." (P-27)	P-24, P-27, P-7
RQ2	Digital Forgery	Partial_Payment_Deception	Intentionally paying a fraction of the agreed amount (e.g., 100 instead of 1000) and counting on the merchant to only glance at the "payment received" notification without verifying the zeros.	3	"He was supposed to give me 1000, gave me 100... I found he had put in less." (P-6)	P-6, P-16, P-22
RQ2	Social Engineering	Fraudulent_Reversal_Request	Scammers sending a fake payment SMS and then immediately calling the victim to claim it was a "mistake," pressuring them to "refund" money that was never actually sent.	6	"Someone calls saying your phone received money by mistake and asks you to send it back." (P-15)	P-4, P-8, P-15, P-19, P-20, P-22
RQ2	Social Engineering	Fake_Prize_Phishing	Scammers contacting users claiming they have won a prize (e.g., from MTN) but requiring a "deposit" or fee to release the winnings.	2	"The fraudster lied to me and told me I had won 400,000 francs... asked me to go to an agent and deposit 7,000." (P-4)	P-4, P-15
RQ2	Social Engineering	Rush_Hour_Exploitation	Fraudsters deliberately targeting merchants during peak/busy times (evening, rain, rush hour) knowing verification rigor is lower due to time pressure.	5	"It happens more when you are stressed... if it fails, you may give them the phone to do it themselves." (P-19)	P-3, P-11, P-19, P-22, P-27
RQ2	Social Engineering	Distraction_Theft	Creating confusion (e.g., claiming urgency, creating a scene) to bypass verification or steal the device.	3	"They pretend to be in a hurry—maybe on a motorcycle—and pressure you to send the money quickly." (P-12)	P-6, P-12, P-22
RQ2	Social Engineering	Cross_Network_Impersonation	Using a number from a different network (e.g., Airtel) to send fake messages to a user on another network (e.g., MTN), confusing the recipient's verification of sender ID.	4	"The message was actually a MoMo message sent from an Airtel number. If you don't check carefully, you could lose money this way." (P-10)	P-8, P-10, P-19, P-22
RQ2	Physical Security	Shoulder_Surfing_PIN	Criminals observing the user entering their PIN in public spaces, leading to subsequent device theft and account draining.	5	"When I ask a motorcycle rider to press * to pay you... he watches all the numbers I press... then he might hack and take the money or steal my phone." (P-5)	P-5, P-7, P-11, P-13, P-23
RQ2	Physical Security	Device_Snatch_Risk	The risk of physical theft when displaying the phone screen to a merchant or moto driver for visual verification.	4	"Sometimes, typing the password... they come after you after paying, or they can even take your phone and then run with it." (P-13)	P-7, P-13, P-19, P-26
RQ2	Physical Security	Unauthorized_Menu_Access	Scammers borrowing a victim's phone under the guise of making a call, but secretly accessing the USSD menu to transfer funds or buy airtime.	4	"A passenger may borrow your phone pretending to make a call but instead goes into the Mobile Money menu... Others borrow your phone and use it to buy airtime." (P-7)	P-5, P-7, P-23, P-28
RQ2	Systemic Flaws	Visual_Verification_Blindspot	The structural vulnerability of relying on the payer's device for proof, which places the merchant at the mercy of whatever the payer chooses to display (edited or real).	8	"If you look into the recovery process... effectively the money is gone." (P-14)	P-6, P-10, P-11, P-19, P-22, P-24, P-25, P-28
RQ2	Systemic Flaws	Notification_Sound_Spoofing	Merchants trusting the "beep" of an incoming SMS as proof of payment without reading the content, which fraudsters exploit by sending non-payment SMSs at the moment of transaction.	3	"Usually, we're in a hurry, so when the phone pings, you think it's the real thing." (P-15)	P-15, P-16, P-28
RQ2	Systemic Flaws	Network_Latency_Gap	The time gap between payment and SMS delivery creates a "trust void" where merchants are forced to guess if a customer is honest or lying.	5	"Sometimes messages are delayed or don't come at all. There are real risks." (P-2)	P-2, P-4, P-15, P-21, P-22
RQ2	Insider Threats	Employee_Collusion/Theft	Staff members exploiting shared PINs or lack of owner oversight to steal funds or collude with fraudsters.	3	"Only between workers, through trying to guess each other's PINs." (P-9)	P-9, P-11, P-28
RQ2	Systemic Flaws	Recovery_Friction	The difficulty, cost, and time required to reverse fraudulent transactions discourages users from pursuing small losses, emboldening fraudsters.	3	"If you look into the recovery process, you'll find the cost and that it takes a long time, so effectively the money is gone." (P-14)	P-9, P-12, P-14
RQ2	Social Engineering	Sympathy_Scams	Fraudsters fabricating emergencies (e.g., accidents, hospital bills) to manipulate merchants or agents into sending money urgently without proper verification.	2	"They once told me that a younger brother had an accident... and asked us to give 15k to take him to the hospital... tell you to send the money quickly." (P-6)	P-6, P-15
RQ2	Physical Security	Hit-and-Run_Fraud	Customers initiating a transaction or feigning payment and physically fleeing the scene (e.g., on a moto or into a crowd) before the merchant can verify.	4	"The rider would think the message is coming, then he would leave, and they'd wait for the money in vain." (P-3)	P-3, P-15, P-22, P-27
RQ2	Systemic Flaws	Account_Lockout_DoS	Attackers intentionally entering wrong PINs on a victim's phone (or during a transaction) to lock the victim's SIM/MoMo account, disrupting their business and preventing verification.	2	"Since they don't know your PIN, they try several times, and your account gets locked... As he left, he managed to block the money transfer, and even my SIM card got locked." (P-5)	P-5, P-7
RQ2	Social Engineering	Ambiguous_Recipient_Claim	Fraudsters claiming they paid to a "company number" or a "boss's number" to confuse an employee who cannot immediately verify that specific account.	2	"That passenger told him they paid to the company number and besides, they had agreed to pay on his number." (P-22)	P-14, P-22
RQ2	Social Engineering	Implicit_Trust_Exploitation	Exploiting cultural norms or physical appearance (e.g., being well-dressed) to bypass verification checks, as merchants feel rude suspecting "respectable" people.	3	"Sometimes you meet a well-dressed person... I once carried a very respectable lady... later, when I checked, she hadn't paid." (P-15)	P-10, P-15, P-22
RQ2	Systemic Flaws	Verification_Fatigue	The cognitive exhaustion from checking every single transaction, leading merchants to eventually lower their guard and stop checking after a period of vigilance.	2	"At first, you feel like no one will ever trick you again, but after a week, you forget." (P-15)	P-11, P-15
RQ3	Financial Exposure	Involuntary_Balance_Display	The distress caused by the automatic display of the remaining account balance in the SMS/USSD confirmation, which users feel is irrelevant to the merchant.	18	"What I think is not important is that... it shouldn't be necessary for him to see my remaining balance. That should stay private." (P-5)	P-2, P-3, P-5, P-6, P-7, P-11, P-12, P-13, P-15, P-16, P-18, P-19, P-20, P-22, P-23, P-24, P-25, P-28
RQ3	Financial Exposure	Predatory_Targeting_Fear	The fear that exposing a high balance will mark the user as a target for physical theft, robbery, or scamming by observers.	9	"Someone could look at it... instantly know my balance, and try to take advantage of me or steal from me." (P-6)	P-3, P-5, P-6, P-7, P-21, P-22, P-23, P-25, P-28
RQ3	Financial Exposure	Poverty_Shaming_Anxiety	The embarrassment or social stigma associated with displaying a very low or zero balance to merchants or peers.	4	"They might see the message, think I received that money... and target me for theft." (P-25)	P-4, P-19, P-22, P-24
RQ3	Financial Exposure	Debt_Recovery_Exposure	The fear that showing a positive balance will prompt merchants or acquaintances to demand repayment of outstanding debts they otherwise claimed they couldn't pay.	2	"I might owe someone 200,000... if they see that I still have a balance higher than what I owe them, they may get angry." (P-19)	P-19, P-12
RQ3	Financial Exposure	Merchant_Pricing_Bias	Concern that merchants might adjust prices or deny bargaining leverage if they see the customer has a substantial balance.	2	"Maybe they might see your remaining balance and think you're rich." (P-24)	P-24, P-4
RQ3	Physical Interaction	PIN_Entry_Vulnerability	The anxiety that bystanders or merchants are intentionally watching the PIN entry process (shoulder surfing) to compromise the account.	9	"When I ask a motorcycle rider to press * to pay you... he watches all the numbers I press... then he might hack." (P-5)	P-5, P-7, P-8, P-9, P-10, P-11, P-13, P-23, P-27
RQ3	Physical Interaction	Device_Handover_Refusal	Strong resistance to handing the unlocked phone to a merchant for verification due to fear of them accessing private data (photos, messages) beyond the payment app.	6	"I wouldn't give my phone for that either. That's not right." (P-4)	P-4, P-10, P-11, P-13, P-15, P-28
RQ3	Physical Interaction	Screen_Shielding_Behavior	Physically turning the body or covering the screen with a hand while typing or showing the confirmation to limit the viewing angle.	4	"If maybe we're there and there are three people, I move back a little and I see how to put it in." (P-27)	P-2, P-8, P-27, P-28
RQ3	Social Dynamics	Inter-Spousal_Secrecy	The desire to keep specific transaction amounts or balances hidden from spouses or partners to maintain financial autonomy.	3	"It could also create conflicts. For example, someone might see that I received money and ask me to explain what I used it for." (P-21)	P-21, P-28, P-15

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RQ3	Social Dynamics	Social_Parasitism_Risk	Fear that friends or relatives identifying a high balance will feel entitled to ask for loans or financial assistance ("black tax").	3	"Sometimes I have a lot of money and I think they might wonder why I have so much." (P-4)	P-4, P-6, P-22
RQ3	Social Dynamics	Employee_Balance_Blindness	Business owners wanting to hide the total accumulated capital in the merchant account from their own employees to prevent theft or wage dissatisfaction.	3	"I wouldn't like it because I want balance to be mine. Feeling you showed it to employees I wouldn't like it." (P-18)	P-18, P-19, P-28
RQ3	Data Persistence	Inbox_Deletion_Hygiene	The habit of immediately deleting payment SMS notifications to prevent them from being viewed if the phone is accessed later.	2	"I delete the message... if it remains visible, someone else could read them, and it could end badly." (P-25)	P-25, P-28
RQ3	Data Persistence	Message_Editing_Workaround	Forwarding the payment SMS to an editor or another number to manually delete the balance line before showing it to the merchant.	3	"When I am forwarding the message, I remove the balance of money I have." (P-4)	P-4, P-19, P-22
RQ3	Identity Exposure	Phone_Number_Leakage	Concern that the transaction reveals the user's personal phone number to strangers (merchants), leading to harassment or unwanted calls.	3	"Just like they hide the phone number... without it always being visible." (P-6)	P-6, P-15, P-19
RQ3	Identity Exposure	Name_Visibility_Anxiety	Unease regarding the full legal name being displayed to every merchant, though often accepted as a necessary trade-off for trust.	2	"Still seeing a person's name and their telephone number makes them visible to everyone." (P-6)	P-6, P-14
RQ3	Design Flaw	Context-Insensitive_Display	Frustration that the interface displays the same level of sensitive detail regardless of whether the user is in a private home or a crowded market.	3	"In a shop counter a merchant cannot easily run away, but outside it is possible." (P-19)	P-7, P-19, P-22
RQ3	Trust Trade-off	Privacy_vs_Trust_Dilemma	The conscious realization that users must sacrifice their privacy (showing balance) to gain the merchant's trust and leave with their goods.	5	"If I don't show him the confirmation message, he may start doubting me... Yet I also remain worried that he immediately knows my balance." (P-5)	P-5, P-17, P-20, P-24, P-25
RQ3	Identity Exposure	Future_Harassment_Anxiety	The fear that merchants will use the phone number captured during the transaction to call the user later for solicitation, begging, or scams.	4	"Before, when you paid someone like a peanut seller, they could keep bothering you by calling... Some even used it to scam you." (P-19)	P-6, P-19, P-22, P-15
RQ3	Social Dynamics	Language-Induced_Privacy_Loss	Users who cannot read English/French notifications are forced to show their screens to others for translation, involuntarily exposing their financial data.	2	"Messages sometimes come in English, which makes it difficult... [implies needing help/showing screen]." (P-11)	P-11, P-2
RQ3	Physical Interaction	Bystander_Screen_Glare	The anxiety that other customers in the queue (not just the merchant) can see the balance or PIN when the user holds up their phone.	3	"If maybe we're there and there are three people, I move back a little and I see how to put it in." (P-27)	P-7, P-27, P-28
RQ3	Financial Exposure	Spending_Power_Inference	The concern that a merchant will judge the customer's lifestyle or purchasing power based on the disparity between the transaction amount and the account balance.	2	"Sometimes I have a lot of money and I think they might wonder why I have so much." (P-4)	P-4, P-24
RQ3	Design Flaw	Data_Minimization_Expectation	The specific user belief that the system is "broken" or "badly designed" simply because it displays data (balance) that is functionally useless for the proof of payment.	5	"What I think they shouldn't see is the balance, because I don't think it's necessary." (P-3)	P-3, P-5, P-11, P-13, P-15
RQ3	Physical Interaction	Unattended_Device_Anxiety	The fear of leaving a phone charging or unattended at a shop because the SMS previews (showing balance) appear on the lock screen.	2	"If I put it down, someone could look at it... instantly know my balance... try to take advantage." (P-6)	P-6, P-23
RQ4	Privacy Interface	Split-Screen_Balance_Hiding	A UI design that segregates the transaction confirmation (Screen 4a/5a) from the account balance (Screen 4b/5b), allowing users to show proof of payment without revealing their financial status.	14	"This one would be better, because it shows the payer their own details, the amount paid, and their name, but my balance doesn't appear." (P-3)	P-3, P-5, P-7, P-11, P-12, P-13, P-15, P-16, P-20, P-22, P-23, P-24, P-19, P-25
RQ4	Privacy Interface	Secondary_Balance_Navigation	The specific interaction model (e.g., pressing 'N' or 'Next') to access the private balance screen only when the user explicitly chooses to see it.	4	"You would press 'n' and then continue to see your balance. But normally you are the one controlling your account." (P-24)	P-6, P-24, P-16, P-28
RQ4	Privacy Interface	Phone_Number_Masking	Hiding or masking digits of the customer's phone number on the merchant's screen to prevent future harassment or data misuse.	2	"The phone number should be removed so that only the symbols of that number are visible." (P-6)	P-6, P-15
RQ4	Anti-Fraud Tool	Merchant-Defined_Dynamic_Secret	A security feature where the merchant sets a variable secret code (daily/weekly) that must appear on the customer's confirmation screen to prove the transaction is live and not a screenshot.	14	"If at that moment they have to show my password (code) and it's not there, I would immediately know it's fake." (P-3)	P-3, P-5, P-7, P-8, P-10, P-11, P-13, P-16, P-17, P-20, P-21, P-19, P-27, P-28
RQ4	Anti-Fraud Tool	Merchant-Entered_Confirmation	A protocol where the merchant physically enters a code on the customer's device to finalize the transaction, ensuring the merchant has direct control over the confirmation.	6	"Your secret number is what you would use to ensure you get paid... because you are the one confirming it." (P-24)	P-12, P-24, P-16, P-21, P-23, P-27
RQ4	Anti-Fraud Tool	Timestamp_Integration	The mandatory inclusion of a clear Date and Time stamp on the primary confirmation screen to help merchants identify recycled screenshots.	10	"The difference is that this one shows the date and time... I think this message is much better." (P-7)	P-7, P-15, P-16, P-20, P-22, P-24, P-25, P-4, P-19, P-28
RQ4	Anti-Fraud Tool	Sender_Identity_Field	Adding the sender's legal Name to the confirmation screen (which is currently missing in some USSD pop-ups) to facilitate cross-checking with ID or social familiarity.	9	"If names were also displayed along with the number, that would be fine." (P-11)	P-10, P-11, P-13, P-15, P-16, P-22, P-24, P-19, P-25
RQ4	Anti-Fraud Tool	Service_Authenticity_Header	Including explicit branding (e.g., "Mobile Money" header, "Yello") to distinguish legitimate system messages from fake SMS or notes.	3	"For me, it is very important that M-Money is shown... Earlier (screen 1), there was 'thank you for using Mobile Money.'" (P-19)	P-10, P-19, P-22
RQ4	Delegation Feature	Multi-Recipient_Notification	A feature allowing transaction receipts to be sent simultaneously to the business owner and an employee/partner/spouse to enable remote monitoring.	9	"It's a good solution because it will help in tracking and controlling what goes in and out." (P-13)	P-8, P-13, P-16, P-17, P-19, P-23, P-24, P-25, P-27
RQ4	Delegation Feature	Role-Based_Data_Access	Configuring multi-recipient notifications so that the business owner sees full details (including balance) while the employee sees only the transaction amount.	3	"Except the employee doesn't see balance I would like that. Because if they're the one who paid they would know they were paid without asking me." (P-18)	P-18, P-19, P-28
RQ4	Delegation Feature	Remote_Supervision_Utility	Using multi-recipient notifications to manage a business or handle sales when the owner is physically absent or traveling.	5	"Have access to payments that happened when you're not there. I like it because it would solve when I was left with others." (P-17)	P-17, P-24, P-16, P-19, P-23
RQ4	Resistance Factor	Physical_Handover_Resistance	Strong user pushback against designs that require handing the unlocked phone to a stranger/merchant due to theft or privacy fears.	9	"It's not good because it's not safe." (P-8)	P-8, P-10, P-11, P-13, P-15, P-17, P-4, P-28, P-19
RQ4	Resistance Factor	Manual_Verification_Fatigue	User pushback against designs that increase the workload per transaction (entering codes) during busy periods.	5	"You're going to overwhelm us... It's a lot of work; you constantly have to change the PIN." (P-4)	P-4, P-6, P-8, P-13, P-27
RQ4	Resistance Factor	Education_Barrier_Concern	Concern that complex security features (like changing daily codes) might be too difficult for uneducated or elderly users to adopt.	1	"It would be hard for an older woman in the village to understand... It would help educated people, yes." (P-15)	P-15
RQ4	Information Hierarchy	Screen_Clutter_Reduction	Removing non-essential information (like "Zero Transaction Fees" or balance) to make the proof of payment clearer and faster to read.	1	"They could also remove 'zero transaction fee,' because the customer already knows that no fees were charged." (P-19)	P-19, P-12
RQ4	Configuration Preference	Code_Rotation_Frequency	Merchant preferences for how often security codes should change (Daily vs. Shift-based) to balance security with convenience.	3	"I feel I'd put it in the morning, now after 6 hours I'd change it... Before 6 hours there are many customers." (P-27)	P-11, P-17, P-27
RQ4	Information Hierarchy	Transaction_ID_Tracking	Including a unique Transaction ID on the confirmation screen to assist with bank reconciliations and dispute resolution.	2	"This is mainly asked by the bank... If it doesn't arrive, that's when the bank asks for it." (P-10)	P-10, P-12
RQ4	Social Design	Spousal_Financial_Transparency	Using multi-recipient notifications specifically to coordinate household finances or joint businesses with a spouse.	2	"It would be good, it would help us because for example my madam and I go to the market day always... getting messages to all of us would be good." (P-27)	P-27, P-21
RQ4	Security Feature	PIN_Length_Extension	Increasing the length of the PIN/Secret Code (e.g., beyond 4-5 digits) to make it harder for bystanders to memorize via shoulder surfing.	1	"Maybe the PIN code is a bit short—sometimes it's easy for someone to memorize it quickly; it would be better if it were longer." (P-23)	P-23
RQ4	Data Persistence	Persistent_Digital_Receipts	A preference for SMS-based or App-based receipts that can be stored and retrieved later (unlike flash USSD messages) for dispute resolution.	2	"I have this message here, even if you used it for a year, you could retrieve it. It doesn't meet quality standards at all [referring to transient messages]." (P-4)	P-4, P-15
RQ4	Delegation Feature	Third-Party_Integration	The ability to forward payment notifications not just to SMS, but to social platforms like WhatsApp groups for easier business management.	1	"Optional, could go to another number or WhatsApp group." (P-2)	P-2
RQ4	Verification Logic	Deductive_Balance_Indicator	A design request (specifically from merchants) to see a "Balance Decreased" indicator or delta, rather than the absolute balance, to prove funds actually left the account without revealing total wealth.	2	"If I don't see a decrease in their balance, how do I know they really paid?...When you see a line that says 'remaining balance,' you can tell that the money has actually left." (P-15)	P-15, P-28
RQ4	User Experience	Error_Anxiety_Reduction	Design workflows (like Merchant-Entered Code) that shift the burden of accuracy to the merchant, reducing the customer's fear of typing the wrong number.	1	"Trust would be very high and it would reduce the fear of making mistakes." (P-16)	P-16
RQ4	Localization	Local_Language_Default	Ensuring confirmation messages are displayed in Kinyarwanda by default to prevent users from needing help (and thus exposing screens) to interpret English messages.	2	"Messages sometimes come in English, which makes it difficult for us to know when it went through." (P-11)	P-7, P-11

Research Question	Category	Code	Definition	Number of Participants	Example Quotes	Participants falling in this code
RQ4	Visual Authenticity	App-Like_Visual_Fidelity	A preference for interfaces that look like modern smartphone applications rather than basic text, perceived as harder to forge.	2	"I'm not sure if this one is from an app or something else — it might be from an application... This one looks good." (P-15)	P-15, P-24